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Research Article

**TYPE 2 DIABETES IS EITHER LINKED WITH CANCER OR
NOT? STUDY HELD TO KNOW ABOUT THE PERCENTAGE
OF RISK OF CANCER WITH DIABETES IN MAYO HOSPITAL
LAHORE**

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Abstract:

We performed study in mayo hospital Lahore to study the causally association of cancer risk in mayo hospital Lahore in form 2 diabetes patients. This experiment is under taken from mayo hospital Lahore. This study includes the study of that if one patient has form 2 diabetes it is a chance to patient that it must be a cancer. Or it leads to a cancer. This odd ratio was 1.14 1.08 1.07 0.89 and 0.93 for pancreatic. It is also observed that form 2 diabetes patients were introduced in the method of Meta analysics. It is obtained that the there is a small proof that the casual association. This research contains correct for several cancers. The form 2 diabetes and the disease the cancer are both global issue. By the effect of these two diseases form that these two diseases lead many peoples to death. By studying it is observed that approximately 5.2 and 8.8 million deaths in 2015 year in all the world. It is also observed that type two diabetes have major cause of cancer. Type two diabetes is also associated with colorectal liver kidney uterine and breast cancer.

KEYWORDS: Mayo hospital Lahore, cancer, form 2 diabetes, breast cancer

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INTRODUCTION:

Form 2 diabetes is a serious type of diabetes in patient. It is a spreading disease in all the world [1]. The purpose of this study is to find the answer of 1 question. The question is that is form 2 diabetes is a cause of cancer or not [2]. It is observed that the form 2 this form 2 is really in touch with the liver kidney uterine or breast cancer. This both diseases are a life taking diseases in our entire world [3]. According to one study it is observed that over the 5.0 and 8.7 million death recorded in 2015 year [4]. We did this study in a mayo hospital Lahore by using Mendelian randomization [5]. By detection of this form 2 diabetes causally associated with cancer risk it is performed in mayo hospital Lahore that three studies MR experiment leads to assess the casuals of liability to form 2 diabetes patient that have risk of cancer. So by this purpose a bidirectional MR study for pancreatic cancer [6]. We also performed analysis studies [7]. It is a very serious issue in all the world of form 2 diabetes and cancer patients [8]. This two disease takes many people's lives. We take this serious because of 5 to million peoples died in 2015 [9]. So from this it is observed that this two diseases form 2 diabetes and cancer takes many people lives [10]. So it is important for us to find that it is really form 2 diabetes is associated with cancer breast cancer or another serious. So for this purpose we use different methods to find this answer. We use bidirectional MR study for pancreatic cancer and meta-analysis for FG FI levels [11].

METHODOLOGY:

The two major methods we use for this purpose. Firstly, is diabetes genetics replication and other is Meta analysis. Meta analysis of two main chemicals are compared with pancreatic disease consortium breast cancer in mayo hospital Lahore. The information of disease is discovered by the mayo

hospital Lahore. There are many participants. All the data is taken from mayo hospital Lahore. This study is important for us to find it because this two diseases is a live taking disease in all our the world. The variable selection for form 2 diabetes and FG analysis 33 75000 form 2 diabetes disease and 9000000 control subjects have. The instruments variable taken from Mayo hospital Lahore. It is also observed that the we observed that this study is performed by using 2 methods. It is also find that 170 manuscripts published before 2019. It is also observed that 2 methods include seven studies were included in meta-analysis. We also extracted data of publication the form 2 diabetes and related traits in this study it is also observed that is any link between cancer and form 2 diabetes. In some study the answer is yeas and according to some study the answer is no. In this study this confusion had been removed completely by using two methods.

RESULTS:

In result it is observed that the in form 2 diabetes patient in over all the sensitivity analyses. We found the evidence it is also in before the eye the genetic review to form 2 diabetes patient of form 2 diabetes patient were 1.17 and for in liver cancer we found 1.14 and we found pancreatic cancer 1.07 and for kidney 1.09 and for uterine cancer we found that 1.07 for cervical chances 1.00 and for melanoma is 0.90. It is showed that similarity analysis the esophageal. It also observed that similarity in the analysis of urine and liver cancer. We also found that positive association between genetically predicted risk of pancreatic cancer and form 2 diabetes was observed the reversed that the one important analysis. We also use method Meta analysis in Meta analysis logs as form 2 diabetes and the life taking disease cancer. It is also found that there is no matching in form 2 diabetes with kidney urine and ovarian cancer. As shown in following figure.

In the above table it is shows that the OR was > 1.6 it is observed that if the test is positive and the important test of a body OR's > 1.6 for kidney utrine cervical and stomach cancer. It is also observed that ORs is <1.6 it has been observed by disease in liver. It is observed that the very important test called meta-analysis it were have not a proof that it there is any bond between the important chemical fg level and the life taking disease cancer. It is also predicted that F1 level shows the proof of that this test is positive bond from the life taking disease cancer and previous experiment for this study.

DISCUSSION:

As we know that diabetes and cancer live taking disease now a days [12]. It is a very spreading disease in all our the world. In the first study it is investigated

the causal [13]. It is also observed that genetic to form 2 diabetes [14]. It is also observed that the positive bond of form 2 diabetes and pancreatic disease it was found that Meta analytics and MR studies [15]. It is also observed that there is a very limited MR proof supporting casual bond. It is also observed that by using meta-analysis of 27 case studied that form 2 diabetes had a higher risk of 11 percent for developing cancer and 17 percent have chances of higher cancer mortality rate [16]. Findings of the present it is observed that the method type analysis have a positive result between form 2 diabetes and pancreatic cancer [17]. By using umbrella meta-analysis of 28 studied in mayo hospital Lahore. When comparing form 2 diabetes patients with control subjects [18].

CONCLUSION:

We know that the diabetes and cancer both have live taking disease. We find the curiousness of these two disease from this research is both of them effects more than 6 to 8 million people in 2015. This study conducted in mayo hospital Lahore it strengthen the evidence in favor of causal in bond with form 2 diabetes have increased the chances of pancreatic kidney uterine and cervical. It is also observed from this study is that it decreases the risk of life taking disease called cancer.. So from this we found the answer of is form 2 diabetes casually in bond with the life taking disease called cancer. The answer is yes it is casually associated with cancer risk and decreases the chances of esophageal and melanoma cancer. Both diseases are dangerous for human so proper care and medication is needed to overcome all issues and get a healthy life.

REFERENCES:

1. Yuan, S., Kar, S., Carter, P., Vithayathil, M., Mason, A. M., Burgess, S., & Larsson, S. C. (2020). Is Form 2 Diabetes Mellitus Causally Associated with Cancer Risk? Evidence From a Two-Sample Mendelian Randomisation Study. *Diabetes*.
2. Burgess, S. (2020). Is Form 2 Diabetes Mellitus Causally Associated with Cancer Risk? Evidence from a Two-Sample Mendelian Randomisation Study.
3. Lawlor, D. A. (2016). Commentary: Two-sample Mendelian randomization: opportunities and challenges. *International journal of epidemiology*, 45(3), 908.
4. Carreras-Torres, R., Johansson, M., Gaborieau, V., Haycock, P. C., Wade, K. H., Relton, C. L., ... & Brennan, P. (2017). The role of obesity, form 2 diabetes, and metabolic factors in pancreatic cancer: a Mendelian randomization study. *JNCI: Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 109(9), dxj012.
5. Burgess, S., Scott, R. A., Timpson, N. J., Smith, G. D., Thompson, S. G., & EPIC-InterAct Consortium. (2015). Using published data in Mendelian randomization: a blueprint for efficient identification of causal risk factors. *European journal of epidemiology*, 30(7), 543-552.
6. Gage, S. H., Jones, H. J., Burgess, S., Bowden, J., Smith, G. D., Zammit, S., & Munafò, M. R. (2017). Assessing causality in associations between cannabis use and schizophrenia risk: a two-sample Mendelian randomization study. *Psychological medicine*, 47(5), 971-980.
7. Hwang, L. D., Lawlor, D. A., Freathy, R. M., Evans, D. M., & Warrington, N. M. (2019). Using a two-sample Mendelian randomization

- design to investigate a possible causal effect of maternal lipid concentrations on offspring birth weight. *International journal of epidemiology*, 48(5), 1457-1467.
8. Davies, N. M., Holmes, M. V., & Smith, G. D. (2018). Reading Mendelian randomisation studies: a guide, glossary, and checklist for clinicians. *Bmj*, 362, k601.
 9. Fang, X., Zuo, J., Zhou, J., Cai, J., Chen, C., Xiang, E., ... & Chen, P. (2019). Childhood obesity leads to adult form 2 diabetes and coronary artery diseases: A 2-sample mendelian randomization study. *Medicine*, 98(32).
 10. Liu, H. M., Hu, Q., Zhang, Q., Su, G. Y., Xiao, H. M., Li, B. Y., ... & Deng, H. W. (2019). Causal effects of genetically predicted cardiovascular risk factors on chronic kidney disease: a two-sample Mendelian randomization study. *Frontiers in genetics*, 10, 415.
 11. Burgess, S., Timpson, N. J., Ebrahim, S., & Davey Smith, G. (2015). Mendelian randomization: where are we now and where are we going?.
 12. Tan, V. Y., Yarmolinsky, J., Lawlor, D. A., & Timpson, N. J. (2019). Letter regarding article, "Associations of obesity and circulating insulin and glucose with breast cancer risk: a Mendelian randomization analysis". *International journal of epidemiology*, 48(3), 1014-1015.
 13. Nowak, C., & Ärnlöv, J. (2018). A Mendelian randomization study of the effects of blood lipids on breast cancer risk. *Nature communications*, 9(1), 1-7.
 14. Inoue, A., & Solon, G. (2010). Two-sample instrumental variables estimators. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 92(3), 557-561.
 15. Noordam, R., Oudt, C. H., Bos, M. M., Smit, R. A., & van Heemst, D. (2018). High-sensitivity C-reactive protein, low-grade systemic inflammation and form 2 diabetes mellitus: A two-sample Mendelian randomization study. *Nutrition, Metabolism and Cardiovascular Diseases*, 28(8), 795-802.
 16. Hartwig, F. P., Davies, N. M., Hemani, G., & Davey Smith, G. (2016). Two-sample Mendelian randomization: avoiding the downsides of a powerful, widely applicable but potentially fallible technique.
 17. Zheng, J., Baird, D., Borges, M. C., Bowden, J., Hemani, G., Haycock, P., ... & Smith, G. D. (2017). Recent developments in Mendelian randomization studies. *Current epidemiology reports*, 4(4), 330-345.
 18. Luo, Q., Wen, Z., Li, Y., Chen, Z., Long, X., Bai, Y., ... & Mo, Z. (2020). Assessment of causality in associations between serum uric acid and risk of schizophrenia: a two-sample bidirectional mendelian randomization study. *Clinical Epidemiology*, 12, 223.
 19. Corbin, L. J., Richmond, R. C., Wade, K. H., Burgess, S., Bowden, J., Smith, G. D., & Timpson, N. J. (2016). BMI as a modifiable risk factor for form 2 diabetes: refining and understanding causal estimates using Mendelian randomization. *Diabetes*, 65(10), 3002-3007.
 20. Yuan, S., Carter, P., Bruzelius, M., Vithayathil, M., Kar, S., Mason, A. M., ... & Larsson, S. C. (2020). Effects of tumour necrosis factor on cardiovascular disease and cancer: A two-sample Mendelian randomization study. *EBioMedicine*, 59, 102956.